
Inclusive Education Enhances Skills

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SUMMARY

Existing Knowledge:

1. Fine motor skills and attention are essential for daily life and academic success in children with mild intellectual disabilities (MID).
2. Inclusive education, integrating children with special needs and typically developing peers, aims to promote social and academic benefits.
3. Special education schools provide individualized programs, but their impact on motor and cognitive development is debated.

New Insights:

1. Children with MID in inclusive classrooms exhibited better fine motor skills and attention levels compared to those in special education schools.
2. A strong positive correlation exists between attention and fine motor skills across both educational settings, with inclusive environments yielding stronger outcomes.
3. Inclusive classrooms may motivate children with MID to improve skills by interacting with and adapting to their typically developing peers.

Putting Research into Practice:

1. Enhance inclusive education programs by fostering peer interactions and collaborative activities to improve motor and cognitive skills.
2. Train teachers in inclusive classrooms to address diverse learning needs while creating stimulating environments.
3. Conduct further research to refine inclusive and special education practices for optimized learning outcomes.

Keywords: inclusive education, fine motor skills, attention, intellectual disabilities, special education, cognitive development

Reference:

Top, E. (2023). Fine motor skills and attention level of individuals with mild intellectual disability getting education in inclusive classrooms and special education schools. *International Journal of Developmental Disabilities*, 69(2), 248–255.
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